

Effectiveness of information booklet on knowledge regarding self administration of insulin injection among diabetes mellitus patients at selected hospitals of shimla, himachal pradesh

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Abstract:

Diabetes Mellitus is a chronic disease presented a worldwide burden. Insulin therapy is a potent and life saving medication but if prescribed or administered inaccurately had the potential to cause harm. Insulin management and prescribing errors are common due to insufficient patient's knowledge and can lead to patient harm and adverse patient outcomes as hypoglycemia leading to patient death. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), India had 69.2 million people living with diabetes in 2015. At the same time, global insulin use is projected to rise from 526 million 1000-unit vials in 2018 to 634 million in 2030 **and** will be highest in Asia (322 million vials in 2030). Insulin therapy is essential for the management of type 1 diabetes. It is also increasingly being used in those with type 2 diabetes to achieve optimal glycaemic control.

Objectives are (a) to assess the pretest knowledge regarding self administration of insulin injection among diabetes mellitus patients. (b) to assess the effectiveness of booklet information among diabetes mellitus patients. (c) to find out the association between pretest knowledge regarding self administration of insulin among diabetes mellitus patients with selected socio -demographic variables. Methods: The study adopted non randomized control group pre test and post test research design and was conducted at selected hospitals of District Shimla. A total of 60 diabetic patients in age range of 35-65 years were selected by convenience sampling technique. A structured knowledge questionnaire was used to assess knowledge of adults regarding self administration of insulin injection. Results: Data analysis was done by descriptive and inferential statistics. The study results had shown that. In diabetes mellitus patient the mean \pm SD for pre-test was 8.47 ± 2.931 and for post-test was 21.17 ± 2.499 having mean difference of 12.700. The independent 't' test had shown that there was significant increase in knowledge regarding self administration of insulin injection in diabetes mellitus patient after giving/ providing information booklet at $p < 0.001$. It means that research hypothesis was accepted i.e. there will be significant difference between the pre-test and the post test knowledge regarding self administration of insulin injection among diabetes mellitus patients after providing the information booklet. It was concluded that

the information booklet was effective in improving knowledge of the adults regarding self administration of insulin injection among diabetes mellitus patients. The improved knowledge in the adults will help to prevent the chance of occurrence of complication due to wrong way of administration of insulin injection.

Keywords:

Insulin therapy, Information booklet, Self administration, Insulin injection, Diabetes mellitus.
